

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTI DISCIPLINARY RESEARCH (IJMR)

Peer Reviewed Journal

**ISSN ISSN: 2277 9302
Vol. VI, Issue 5 (I) September, 2016**

A STUDY OF COST-EFFECTIVENESS IN RELATION TO ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHERS' AND CURRICULUM OF TEACHER EDUCATION COURSE AT MASTER'S LEVEL

Vidyanand S.Khandagale
Shivaji University,
Kolhapur

Abstract

Human being aspires for better life and for it needs income. Higher Education is most effective mode to achieve it. Master level education raises the level of production by enhancing the quality and quantity of the knowledge, capability and skills of individual. In other words it produces human beings with desirable professional knowledge, skills and attitudes thereby enhancing the quality of individuals. Higher Education and the economy are closely interrelated and interdependent. Professional Higher Education enhances the knowledge, capabilities & skills. At the same time proper attitude should be developed. Because teacher carries multiple effects they have strength to transform human being to there best. Students are known by their teachers. So teachers' carries broader responsibility and have to play great role in the development of well round personality. It is very important on the part curriculum framers to keep various perspectives in the mind while framing the syllabus. The curriculum should lead to all round development of an individual as human being and also should prepare and equip to face global challenges in today's competitive world. In the present study researcher have studied cost effectiveness of student Student teacher educators in relation to attitude towards Teachers' and curriculum and found significant moderate and direct relationship between Individual cost and attitude towards teachers. The study reveals a very low and inverse relationship between Individual cost and attitude towards curriculum.

Key words: Cost Effectiveness, Attitude towards teachers, Curriculum, Teacher Education course

Introduction

Higher Education is considered throughout the world to be both individual and social aspiration. For individual education beyond the secondary level is assumed to be the way to social esteem, better paying job expanded life options, individual stimulation and frequently a good time in the pursuit of any or all the above. For societies higher education is assumed to be the key to technology, productivity and the other ingredient of competitive and economic growth. Territory or higher education also shapes and preserves the value that defines a culture. And it is believe to be major engine of social justice, equal opportunity and democracy. Although higher education has advantage you need to pay for it. And, if you are paying for education you need to check effectiveness of it. Effectiveness can be then by various way. Every an individual will have different perception for it. But the most important is development of attitude. If teacher's have positive attitude and good value system definitely student will have good impact. Another important thing is about curriculum, the curricular and co curricular activities conducted in certain course should develop different skill, up-to-date knowledge and motivation to Meta learning. Education is considered as consumption and an investment good. The consumption aspect is generally treated by analyzing the amount spent per head of population. Consumption can be defined as the using up of the good and services having an exchange value. A Product or service is considered to belong to the consumption category when it yields satisfaction (or utility) in a single period only for example a child may go to school not because he likes the school but because he may be enjoying being with friends. Investment is defined as "the investment of money or capital for profitable returns." For example a person's acquiring of knowledge teacher education is an investment because the skill and knowledge acquired through the course are expected to be helpful in getting a job therefore this can be considered as an investment. But if person is studying Sanskrit for his/her own satisfaction without any intention of taking a job the money spend could be considered to be consumption. According to Alfred Marshall "Education is the most valuable of all capital that is invested in human being and therefore consider it as natural investment." Investment in education is aimed not only at consumption that is gratification of immediate desires but also helpful in earning through employment which is a future use a when education is considered consumption. It has nothing to do with labor market however education may treat as

consumption and investment. Thus the nature and extend of demand for higher education is directly related to the nature and the extent of employment opportunities.

The categories of Cost

It may be useful to view four broad category of higher educational cost. First are the basic costs of instruction, categorized by American accounting standard as educational and general. There is the cost of faculty and staff salaries, equipment, libraries, administrative and basic research or scholarship its faculty are expected to do absents special grant or contracts. Second are the cost associated with sponsored research or special activities covered by their own funds or appropriation and that would presumably not be incurred without specifically designated revenues. A third category of costs associated with higher education is the costs of students' living room. Broad clothing laundry enforcement and other expenses that would be incurred whether or not individual was a student. The cost of students living will vary according to whether students live at home with parents or with spares or in a student flat or dormitory. The fourth category of cost is the cost of foregone earning (actually foregone real production.) of the student while disengaged from the productive work force.

Attitude

The main aim of education is to modify behavior at the learner as per the needs and expectations of the society behavior is compared of many attributes, one of which is attitude. Attitude is the ideas that an individual has about an object; a thing or situation and which are influenced by the emotion, beliefs, prejudices, biases or predispositions. They depend upon the individual experience at the intellectual biological, social and emotional level, that is, how he perceives a given things object and so on. Thus one's behavior largely depends upon one's attitude, moreover, different perceptions at their intellectual emotional, social biological level. Thus study of attitudes focuses on how individual acquires favorable or unfavorable attitude towards person, objects, things situation and so on.

Definitions of attitude

According to Thurstone and clave (1929) attitude is "the sum of total of a man's inclination and feelings prejudices or biases, ideas, fear threats and convictions about any specific topic." Allport (1935) defines attitude as a "mental and neural state of readiness organized through experiences, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon individual response to all objects and situations with which it is related.

The preceding definition, emphasis that attitudes are to great extent responsible for the behavior of an individual, however, behavior is determined by characteristic of an individual as well as the situation in which he/she behaves.

Curriculum

There are many competing definitions of Curriculum broadly speaking it is perceived in three ways:-

- 1) From the point of view learner's.
- 2) From the point of view the teacher and institution – school or college and
- 3) As a set of intentions reflected in an organized written from such as subject, content, students, programmer material etc.

However, a common element that characterizes in all its different perspectives is its concern of learner (Pratt 1980:04).The central focus of any curriculum is the students. In respect of higher education, curriculum is described as 'the set of broad interrelated decision about what is thought that characterize the general framework within which teaching is planned and learning takes place.

Need of the Study

The researcher was keenly interested to see cost-effectiveness in relation to attitude towards teacher and curriculum. The teacher education in India is going through the transition state. The rapid increase and fall in the students' enrollment in teacher Education College had raised many questions in education system. Researcher while doing review of the literature it was found that number of studies had been conducted on cost. But there were no study done on cost-effectiveness in relation to attitude towards teacher and curriculum. The researcher wants to study the cost i.e. individual cost paid by an individual and how he feels for the world of Globalization where there are new challenges and competitions. The course curriculum should be keep abreast of so that student will enable with different skills and multiple intelligence. At the same time there attitude towards teacher determine the teacher personality as well as department culture.

Statement of the Problem

"A Study of Cost-Effectiveness in Relation to Attitude towards Teachers' and Curriculum of Teacher Education Course at Master's level"

Aim of Study

To Study of Cost effectiveness i.e. Individual cost of the Student teacher educators from the University of Mumbai and the Savitri bai Phule Pune University in relation to Attitude towards teachers and curriculum.

Objectives of the Study

1. To Study the Individual Cost of Student teacher educators in relation to attitude towards Teachers and curriculum.
2. To Study the relationship between individual cost and attitude towards teachers among Student teacher educators.
3. To Study the relationship between individual cost and attitude towards curriculum among Student teacher educators.
4. To Study the relationship between individual cost and percentage of B.Ed. Marks among Student teacher educators.
5. To compare individual cost among Student teacher educators of the University of Mumbai and the Savitri bai Phule Pune University .
6. To compare attitude towards teachers among Student teacher educators of the University of Mumbai and the Savitri bai Phule Pune University .
7. To compare the attitude towards curriculum of M.Ed. course among Student teacher educators of the University of Mumbai and the Savitri bai Phule Pune University .
8. To compare the percentage of B.Ed. marks among Student teacher educators of the University of Mumbai and the Savitri bai Phule Pune University .

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between individual cost and attitude towards teacher among Student teacher educators.

1. There is no significant relationship between individual cost and attitude towards curriculum of M.Ed. Course among Students.
2. There is no significant relationship between individual cost and percentage of B.Ed. marks among Student teacher educators.
3. There is no significant difference in Individual cost among Student teacher educators of the University of Mumbai and the Savitri bai Phule Pune University .
4. There is no significant difference in Attitude towards teachers between Student teacher educators of the University of Mumbai and the Savitri bai Phule Pune University .
5. There is no significant difference in attitude towards curriculum of M.Ed. course among Student teacher educators between the University of Mumbai and the Savitribai Phule Pune University.
6. There is no significant difference in percentage of B.Ed. marks among Student teacher educators of the University of Mumbai and the Savitribai Phule Pune University .

Methodology

For the present study, the descriptive method is adopted to desire the cost effectiveness of Student teacher educators in relation to their attitude towards teacher and curriculum.

The co-relation method is used to study relationship between,

Individual cost and Attitude toward teachers

Individual cost and Attitude towards curriculum

Individual cost and percentage of B.Ed. marks of Student teacher educators

Researcher has used comparative method of investigate the difference between, the University of Mumbai and the Savitri bai Phule Pune University in terms of the following variables.

- 1) Individual towards of teacher
- 2) Attitude towards of teachers
- 3) Attitude towards of curriculum

- 4) Percentage of B.Ed. marks.

Nature and size of simple

The method of sampling used for percent study was derived through technique of incidental purposive sampling method. For the present study researchers conducted a study of M.Ed. course students from the Department of Education, University of Mumbai and the Department of Education and Extension, Savitri bai Phule Pune University had comprised all.

Tools of Research

The data required for the presents study was the Individual cost, Attitude towards teachers and Curriculum. For the present study following tools are used.

- 1) Individual cost prepared by (Wakpanjan)
- 2) Attitude towards Teachers prepared by (Paralkar)
- 3) Attitude towards curriculum prepared by (Paralkar)

Data Collection

After identifying tools the next step was collecting data. The researcher personally visited Department of Education of both Universities, sought the permission of the Department authority and on the appointed time, data was collected from the Student teacher educators .The investigator after establishing the rapport with the teacher gave them instruction and administrated the tools. The data collected was edited by completeness.

Analysis of Data

- a. Descriptive analysis
- b. Inferential analysis
 - Correlation
 - 't' test
 - 'w' test

Major Findings

There is no significant difference in percentage of B.Ed. marks among Student teacher educators of the University of Mumbai and the University of Pune.

Discussion of the finding and Conclusion

The finding of the study has been discussed follows.

- Relationship between Individual cost and Attitude towards teachers
The study reveals significant moderate and direct relationship between these variables, which could be due to the reason that, as students are spending big amount as tuition fees they expects certain skills from the teachers.
Attitude towards teachers 'contain certain question, which ask how a teacher behave in the Department and how cooperative he/ she is, and centre's the needs of students etc. The data collected from the Department of Education, Savitri bai Phule Pune University which runs this course on unaided basis and the students need to pay heavy tuition fees and are expects development of various skills among them from the Department during the course. The other reason would be students came for M.Ed. after the completion of B.Ed. course, which teaches them to have respect towards teachers.
- Relationship between Individual cost and attitude towards curriculum.
The study reveals a very low and inverse relationship between these two variables. The reason would be the individual cost amount paid for M.Ed. course and non aided department have high fees, the students may feel that they are paying more and the curriculum content, activities skills would be not up to the mark.
- Relationship between Individual cost and percentage of B.Ed. marks.

The study revealed a statistically significant direct relationship between these two variables. The probable reason would be that they are getting good marks in B.Ed. course and develop interest in this course so they don't mind to pay high for it and will get placed in good organisation.

- Difference in Individual cost between the University of Mumbai and of Savitri bai Phule Pune University .The means scores reveal that the University of Pune students pay more fees then that

the University of Mumbai. This is because the course run by the Savitri bai Phule Pune University is unaided, where as the University of Mumbai M.Ed. course is aided, although the other expenses are little high in Mumbai one of the question asked in Individual cost tool was if you would have earned rather than doing M.Ed. course how much you would have earned for this question the Mumbai University students have scored a little high.

- Difference in Attitude towards teachers between the University of Mumbai and the Savitri bai Phule Pune University . The means score reveal that attitude towards teachers from the Savitri bai Phule Pune University is high. This would be because, Student teacher educators are paying high fees they are expecting quality education from the Department teacher. At the same time teachers are Senior in the field of teacher education like to maintain their respect towards students, as most of them are B.Ed. College faculty and are well known in the field of education and most of the students
- Difference of Attitude towards Attitude towards curriculum between the University of Mumbai and University of Pune.

The means score reveals that attitude towards attitude towards curriculum from the University of Mumbai is the little high then the students from Savitri bai Phule Pune University. The probable reason would be Department of Education University of Mumbai gives more exposure to the student's teacher educator. The cosmopolitan nature of Mumbai gives broader exposure and competition as Mumbai is Economical capital of the country. As the Department of Education & Extension of the Savitri bai Phule Pune University is younger compare to other. In spite of good content there is lack of coordination between students and teachers as most of the teachers were visiting faculty.

- Difference in B.Ed. percentage marks between the University of Mumbai and the Savitri bai Phule Pune University.
The means score reveals that Student teacher educators from Savitri bai Phule Pune University are higher than the University of Mumbai. The probable reason would be evaluation criterion and norms followed by the evaluators.

It is necessary to have reason in the field of Economics of Education. As it is the era of Globalization we need to have a practical outlook. As we are looking at students as "Customers" and must be accountable to give delighted service to them, along with Co- operative behavior of teachers there is urgent need to inculcate marketing skills in teaching profession as well as abreast curriculum of global standards..

References

Buch M.B Chief Editor "A Survey of Research in Education, Society for Educational research and Development Baroda.

Best J.W and Kahn J.V (1996) Seventh Edition, New Delhi ,Prentice hall, of India Private Ltd.

Ward Mitchell Gates: "A Practical Guide of Educational research, New Jersey, Prentice hall nic, Eagle wood Cliffs.

Pandya S.R. Administration and Management of Education, Mumbai Himalaya Publishing house.

Garett H.E. Statistics for Psychology and Education,(1996) New York, David Mikay Company Inc.

Gulford J.P and Fruchter B, (1978) Fundamental Statistics in Psychology and Education, USA McGraw Hill Book Company.

Obeyar Heggade (1992) Economics of Education, Mumbai,Himalaya Publishing house.

Web resources

www.nuepa.org

www.education.nic.in
